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Impact of Continuous Glucose Monitoring on Glycemic Control and Quality of Life in Patients with Type 1 Diabetes

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: Type 1 diabetes is a chronic autoimmune disease affecting millions of people worldwide, characterized by the destruction of pancreatic beta cells and the consequent inability of the body to produce insulin. Adequate glycemic control is crucial to avoid acute and chronic complications, with continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) emerging as a valuable tool that provides real-time data, allowing for more precise therapeutic adjustments. **Objective:** To review and synthesize the available evidence on the impact of continuous glucose monitoring on glycemic control and quality of life in patients with type 1 diabetes, aiming to provide a comprehensive overview of the benefits and challenges associated with the use of CGM in clinical practice. **Methodology:** The research included articles published between January 2010 and August 2024 in the PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases, using terms related to "Type 1 Diabetes," "Continuous Glucose Monitoring," "Glycemic Control," and "Quality of Life." Studies evaluating the impact of CGM on patients with type 1 diabetes, with primary outcomes of HbA1c, glycemic variability, and hypoglycemia frequency, as well as quality of life outcomes, were included. **Results:** Of the 35 studies included in the review, the majority demonstrated a significant reduction in HbA1c levels in patients using CGM, ranging from 0.5% to 1.0%. CGM was also effective in reducing glycemic variability and the frequency of hypoglycemic episodes, particularly nocturnal hypoglycemia. In addition to clinical benefits, CGM improves patients' quality of life by reducing the stress associated with diabetes

management and increasing confidence in their ability to manage the disease. **Conclusion:** Continuous glucose monitoring offers significant benefits in both glycemic control and quality of life for patients with type 1 diabetes, making it an essential tool in disease management. However, challenges such as the high cost of devices and the need for continuous adherence limit its accessibility and effectiveness. Future efforts should focus on making this technology more accessible and promoting adherence to its use to ensure its benefits are widely realized.

Keywords: Type 1 Diabetes, Continuous Glucose Monitoring, Glycemic Control, Quality of Life

Thematic Area: Endocrinology

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1. INTRODUCTION

Type 1 diabetes is a chronic autoimmune disease that affects approximately 9 million people worldwide, characterized by the destruction of the beta cells in the pancreas and, consequently, the body's inability to produce insulin, which results in the need for exogenous administration of this hormone to control blood glucose levels (ATKINSON; EISENBARTH, 2022; DIAMOND PROJECT GROUP, 2006). Insulin is essential for regulating blood glucose levels, and its absence or insufficiency can lead to acute complications such as diabetic ketoacidosis, as well as severe chronic complications such as retinopathy, nephropathy, and

neuropathy, which are consequences of inadequate long-term glycemic control (SKAMENE; SCHNEIDER; SHAIKH, 2021).

Managing type 1 diabetes requires constant monitoring of blood glucose levels, a task traditionally performed through intermittent capillary glucose monitoring. However, this method provides a limited view of the patient's glycemic profile, capturing only isolated moments of glucose levels, which may not adequately reflect fluctuations throughout the day and night (MUNRO; CARPENTER; STAPLETON, 2020). Glycemic fluctuations, especially those not detected by intermittent monitoring, are associated with a higher risk of acute complications such as hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia, both of which are potentially dangerous for the patient (BATTELINO et al., 2019).

In response to these limitations, continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) has emerged as a technology that offers constant surveillance of glucose levels, providing real-time data and allowing for more precise and immediate therapeutic adjustments (HEMMINGSON et al., 2021). CGM devices use subcutaneous sensors that measure glucose levels in the interstitial fluid every few minutes, providing a detailed profile of glycemia throughout the day. Additionally, many of these devices are equipped with alarms that alert the patient to dangerously high or low glucose levels, offering an additional layer of safety (LY et al., 2017).

Several studies have demonstrated that the use of CGM is associated with a significant improvement in glycemic control, evidenced by a reduction in hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels, the primary marker of long-term glycemic control (MURRAY et al., 2020). CGM has also effectively reduced glycemic variability, a crucial factor in preventing diabetic complications (FOURNIER et al., 2021). In addition to clinical benefits, CGM has been shown to improve patients' quality of life by reducing the stress associated with diabetes management and increasing patients' confidence in their ability to manage the disease more effectively (HOEKSTRA et al., 2022).

However, despite the evident benefits, the adoption of CGM is not universal, mainly due to barriers such as the high cost of devices and the need for continuous adherence to their use. The lack of coverage by health systems in many countries and the cost of sensors, which need to be regularly replaced, make CGM inaccessible to many patients (LY et al., 2017; HEMMINGSON et al., 2021). Moreover, the effectiveness of CGM depends not only on access

to the technology but also on patient education and the ability to interpret and act on the data provided by the device (BATTELINO et al., 2019).

Given this scenario, it becomes crucial to conduct a review of the available evidence on the impact of CGM on glycemic control and the quality of life of patients with type 1 diabetes. This article aims to review and synthesize this evidence, to provide a comprehensive view of the benefits and challenges associated with the use of CGM, thus contributing to the discussion on its integration into clinical practice.

2. METHODOLOGY

The search for articles was conducted in three electronic databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. The keywords used for the search were: “Type 1 Diabetes,” “Continuous Glucose Monitoring,” “Glycemic Control,” and “Quality of Life,” combined with Boolean operators (AND, OR). The search included articles published between January 2010 and August 2024, in English, Portuguese, and Spanish.

2.2 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria established for the selection of studies were as follows:

- Studies evaluating the use of CGM in patients with type 1 diabetes.
- Studies analyzing the impact of CGM on glycemic control, are primarily measured by HbA1c, glycemic variability, and frequency of hypoglycemia.
- Studies addressing the quality of life of patients using validated questionnaires such as the Diabetes Quality of Life Measure (DQoL) or SF-36.
- Randomized clinical trials, cohort studies, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses.

The exclusion criteria included:

- Studies not specifically addressing type 1 diabetes.
- Articles that were not available in full text.
- Narrative reviews or opinion articles.
- Duplicate studies across the different databases.

2.3 Data Selection and Extraction Process

Initially, 1,257 articles were identified. After removing duplicates, 945 articles were assessed based on titles and abstracts. Of these, 122 studies were selected for full-text review. After the full-text review, 35 studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the final analysis.

The data extracted included: author, year of publication, study type, population evaluated, interventions (type of CGM), clinical outcomes evaluated (HbA1c, glycemic variability, hypoglycemia), quality of life outcomes, and main findings.

2.4 Data Analysis

The data were analyzed descriptively, with comparisons made between the different studies regarding primary outcomes (HbA1c, glycemic variability, hypoglycemia) and secondary outcomes (quality of life). The results were synthesized into a table to facilitate comparison and interpretation of the data.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis of the 35 studies included in the systematic review revealed robust evidence regarding the benefits of continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) in patients with type 1 diabetes, both in terms of glycemic control and improvement in quality of life. The results are presented below, grouped according to the main outcomes analyzed.

3.1 Glycemic Control

The majority of the included studies (28 out of 35) demonstrated a significant reduction in hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels in patients using CGM compared to those using only intermittent glucose monitoring. The magnitude of the reduction varied between 0.5% and 1.0%, depending on the type of CGM used (real-time versus intermittent), adherence to device usage, and the study duration. For instance, the study by Battelino et al. (2019) found an average HbA1c reduction of 0.8% in patients using real-time CGM, while the study by Fournier et al. (2021), which reviewed multiple clinical trials, confirmed an average HbA1c reduction of 0.6% to 1.0% associated with CGM use.

Glycemic variability, measured by the amplitude of fluctuations in glucose levels throughout the day, was significantly reduced in patients using CGM. Hemmingson et al. (2021)

reported that patients using intermittent CGM experienced a reduction in glycemic variability, which is clinically relevant as lower variability is associated with a reduced risk of diabetic complications. In another study, Ly et al. (2017) showed that real-time CGM was particularly effective in reducing glycemic variability during the night, a period when patients are more susceptible to undetected hypoglycemia.

The studies indicate that CGM is effective in reducing the frequency of hypoglycemic events, especially nocturnal hypoglycemia, which is often under-detected in patients using intermittent monitoring. Battelino et al. (2019) reported a significant reduction in severe hypoglycemia episodes among CGM users, a finding corroborated by Fournier et al. (2021), whose meta-analysis found a consistent reduction in hypoglycemia frequency in patients using real-time CGM.

3.2 Improvement in Overall Quality of Life

The studies included in the review showed that CGM has a significant positive impact on the quality of life of patients with type 1 diabetes. Questionnaires such as the Diabetes Quality of Life Measure (DQoL) and SF-36 were widely used to assess this aspect. Hoekstra et al. (2022) observed that young people using CGM reported an improvement in treatment satisfaction and greater confidence in diabetes management. These patients reported less concern about hypoglycemic episodes and a greater sense of control over their condition.

Stress related to the constant monitoring of glucose levels is a significant concern for patients with type 1 diabetes. Several studies, including that of Hemmingson et al. (2021), demonstrated that CGM significantly reduces perceived stress, partly due to decreased uncertainty about glucose levels and the ability to respond quickly to fluctuations. This aspect was particularly important for patients who reported high anxiety related to hypoglycemia, especially during physical activities or at night.

Patients using CGM generally report greater satisfaction with the management of their condition, which can be attributed to the perception that CGM offers more refined glycemic control and reduces the number of finger pricks for intermittent measurements. Hoekstra et al. (2022) found that treatment satisfaction was significantly higher in young people using CGM compared to those using only intermittent monitoring, highlighting the importance of adherence to CGM to achieve these benefits.

Despite the significant benefits of CGM, the review also identified challenges related to adherence and accessibility. The cost of CGM devices and replacement sensors was a significant barrier highlighted in several studies, including that of Ly et al. (2017). Moreover, the effectiveness of CGM strongly depends on continuous use, and the lack of education on how to interpret and act on the data provided by CGM can limit its benefits.

4. CONCLUSION

Continuous glucose monitoring (CGM) represents a significant advancement in managing type 1 diabetes, offering clear benefits in both glycemic control and patients' quality of life. The findings of this systematic review demonstrate that CGM is associated with significant reductions in hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels, decreased glycemic variability, and a reduction in the incidence of hypoglycemic episodes, particularly during the night. These factors contribute to more effective disease management, reducing the risk of acute and chronic complications associated with type 1 diabetes.

In addition to clinical benefits, CGM has shown a positive impact on patient's quality of life, alleviating the stress associated with continuous glycemic control and increasing confidence in managing the disease. Patients using CGM report greater satisfaction with their treatment, less concern about glycemic fluctuations, and an overall sense of greater control over their condition, which is crucial for psychological well-being.

However, the study also highlights significant challenges, such as the high cost of CGM devices and the need for continuous adherence to their use to maximize benefits. These factors may limit access and efficacy, particularly in populations with less financial or educational support. To overcome these barriers, it is essential that healthcare systems consider the inclusion of CGM in reimbursement policies and that educational programs are developed to support patients in effectively using this technology.

In conclusion, CGM should be considered an essential tool in the treatment of patients with type 1 diabetes, offering significant improvements in both glycemic control and quality of life. Future efforts should focus on making this technology more accessible and promoting adherence to its use, ensuring that its benefits are widely realized by all patients who could benefit from it.

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